

Synthesis and Characterizations of Ni-doped Perovskite-Type Oxides for Effective CO₂ methanation

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Abstract

The emission of greenhouse gases (GHGs) especially carbon dioxide (CO₂) due to burning of fossil fuels is persistently damaging the ecosystem [1]. There is urgent need to mitigate the level of CO₂ and develop the sustainable energy systems to achieve the zero-emission target set by the EU countries upto 2050. Among the existing technologies for CO₂ utilization, methanation is an efficient route not only to mitigate the CO₂ concentration, but also partially fulfill the energy requirements [2]. The Ni-based catalysts are widely used with acceptable CO₂ conversion. Their catalytic activity depends upon redox properties, basic sites, metal dispersion and resistance against deactivation problem. To design advanced Ni-based redox catalysts with high activity, stability (lower sintering) and coke deposits, the metal oxide promoters like Fe₂O₃ or Y₂O₃ is considered useful to improve and overcome these issues [3].

This work proposes Ni metal supported over rare earth-based emerging perovskite-type oxides as potential catalysts for the CO₂ methanation. Presence of oxygen vacancies in perovskite-like materials enable them to exhibit higher catalytic activity [4]. Furthermore, to tune the surface basicity, metal-support interaction and to enhance the activation of CO₂, rare earth metals (La, Ce, etc.) are considered best candidates [5].

In view of the above, different perovskite-type supports (A_xMn_xO₃, A= La, Ce) based on A-side substitution of rare earth metals were prepared with Ni metal loading of 10 wt.% via impregnation method. The catalysts were characterized using XRD, and H₂-

TPR techniques. The CO₂ methanation was carried out in a tubular reactor connected to digital Micrometric PID Eng & Tech face controller and ABB AO2020 analyzer equipped with Caldos 25 and Uras 26 detection units as shown in Figure 1. The catalytic activity was assessed in the temperature range of 200–550 °C and at a space velocity of 12,000 h⁻¹.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram for the experimental setup

The Ce-based catalyst exhibited ca. 30 % higher conversion compared to the La-based one at 400 °C, with better CH₄ selectivity and redox properties. Partial substitution of A-side Ce cations via the solution combustion method resulted in high crystallinity, higher CO₂ conversion and superior redox properties. This reveals the influence of the support material on redox properties and metal-support interaction and highlights the potential of Ce-based perovskites catalysts for the CO₂ methanation system.

Keywords: CO₂ methanation, Perovskites, Ni-Catalysts, Rare earth metals

References

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